

Lessons from a multi-country study into persistent and recrudescient trachoma

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Abstract:

This article summarises the key lessons learned from a six-country study that collected data on complementary indicators related to *Chlamydia trachomatis* infection to better understand persistent and recrudescing trachoma. It highlights the practical challenges associated with adding these complementary indicators to routine trachoma surveys (often called ‘plus’ surveys) and suggests ways to address them. Although more complicated and costly to conduct, ‘plus’ surveys can improve data for programmatic decision-making and may enable some countries to reach elimination targets sooner.

Keywords: Conjunctival swabs, Dried blood spots, Polymerase chain reaction, Serology, Surveys, Trachoma

Introduction

Trachoma, caused by the bacterium *Chlamydia trachomatis* (*Ct*), is the leading infectious cause of blindness. It is targeted for global elimination as a public health problem by the year 2030.¹ While progress toward elimination has focused on grading the active trachoma clinical sign trachomatous inflammation—follicular (TF) and estimating TF prevalence among children, the World Health Organization (WHO) Informal Consultation on End-Game Challenges for Trachoma Elimination recommended that complementary indicators related to *Ct* infection be used to help inform tailored management in evaluation units (EUs) with persistent TF (an EU with at least two impact surveys at which TF is $\geq 5\%$, without ever having had a TF $< 5\%$) or recrudescing TF (an EU with at least one surveillance survey at which TF is $\geq 5\%$).² This is because the presence of TF is poorly correlated with evidence of conjunctival *Ct* infection, especially following antibiotic mass drug administration (MDA).³ The lag in TF resolution may result in unnecessary rounds of MDA if the prevalence of TF remains above the 5% threshold for stopping MDA despite little evidence of *Ct* transmission.

Trachoma prevalence surveys that collect population-based data on anti-*Ct* antibodies and/or ocular *Ct* infection are referred to here as ‘plus’ surveys. These surveys follow the standard Tropical Data methodology⁴ but add the collection of dried blood spots (DBS) for serology and/or conjunctival swabs for nucleic acid amplification testing (including polymerase chain reaction (PCR)). Collection of these complementary indicators impact survey planning, training, fieldwork, data analysis and data access; it also introduces laboratory work. Although more complicated and costly to conduct, in the context of persistent and recrudescing TF, the ‘plus’ design aims to generate better

data for programmatic decision-making, and may enable some EUs to stop MDA sooner, thus expediting the path to elimination.

This article summarises the lessons learned from a six-country study that implemented the ‘plus’ survey design - and a number of mixed method tools – to confirm the presence of and understand factors associated with persistent and recrudescing TF in Cameroon, Ethiopia, Kenya, Nigeria, Uganda and Zambia.⁵ It reflects on the practical challenges associated with conducting ‘plus’ surveys to share lessons with countries hoping to undertake or scale up such surveys for routine programmatic use.

Key lessons

1. Start your planning early, as supply chain problems can pose major delays

‘Plus’ surveys necessitate the procurement of additional supplies to facilitate the collection, storage, transportation and processing of specimens. While some items may be procured locally, many of the more specialist supplies need to be procured internationally. Expertise in generating certificates of donation, certificates of origin and import permits to get supplies efficiently through customs may be needed. Moreover, attention must be given to cold chain shipping requirements, as maintaining the integrity of temperature-sensitive materials (e.g. laboratory reagents) is critical to ensure the validity of results.

In the study, supply chain problems manifested in a variety of ways: ordering the right type and quantity of supplies; navigating customs regulations and clearances; determining how to distribute supplies once they arrived in country; and managing delays in fieldwork when supplies were delayed or held up in customs. The overarching lesson is to allow at least three months’ lead time for procurement.

Tropical Data (a service that supports national programmes to conduct trachoma prevalence surveys)³ is creating supporting resources to help countries navigate these challenges. Additionally, programmes should ensure they work through established channels in-country with expertise in supply importation, such as health ministry logistics systems.

2. Cold chain for samples requires effort to set up and maintain

A cold chain is needed to maintain the integrity of specimens collected as part of ‘plus’ surveys. In most trachoma-endemic countries, cold chain capacities have been built at sub-national levels by vaccination programmes and public health laboratories that can be utilised for ‘plus’ surveys. Nevertheless, time should be set aside at the planning stage to confirm (preferably through visual inspection) that facilities and equipment are

fully functioning and available to the trachoma programme, e.g. to facilitate the need for daily ice pack rotation when swabs are being collected.

The cold chain also requires supervision during the fieldwork stage to ensure facilities and equipment remain fit-for-purpose. In one study country, the central facility identified to provide refrigeration encountered power issues, meaning a second (private) facility had to be found at short notice, incurring extra costs. Country programmes should factor contingency plans into the supply budget to ensure the cold chain can be maintained.

3. Additional community sensitisation is needed for the collection of blood and/or conjunctival swabs

In this study, there were concerns about the acceptability of sample collection in the different study sites. Subsequently, extra care was taken to address concerns and build trust in stakeholders and communities at every stage of the survey process. It is important to prioritise sensitisation efforts during implementation planning (e.g. including community and religious leaders and government officials in discussions), and to ensure that tailored messaging is included in ethics submissions, participant information sheets and consent/assent forms to clarify the purpose, safety and benefits of these procedures.

4. Dedicate extra time and resources to survey team trainings and supervision

'Plus' surveys introduce new team roles and responsibilities, including the duties associated with a specimen manager to oversee the collection of samples. We recommend countries add at least one extra day to the standard Tropical Data training schedule⁴ and allow more time for field practice. Country programmes should also order extra sample collection supplies to support classroom and field training exercises.

Due to their added complexity, 'plus' surveys require more supervision than standard trachoma surveys. Teams that are new to these surveys require close supervision in the early days to ensure they are following the standard operating procedures for specimen collection and storage. In addition to providing technical supervision, supervisors will also be required to oversee logistical issues (e.g. the cold chain).

5. The lateral flow assay for serology testing is feasible for local laboratories to implement

An emphasis was placed on using laboratories based in the study countries to analyse specimens. Serological testing was conducted using either a lateral flow assay (LFA) to measure antibodies against the *Ct* antigen Pgp3 (four of the six countries) or a Pgp3 multiplex bead assay (two of the six countries).⁶ Two of the LFA trainings were done in person, one was done by another in-country lab using a remote train-the-trainer model, and one was done fully remotely. The four laboratories that used the LFA found it easy to learn, and this experience demonstrated the potential to use virtual trainings going forward.

6. Country laboratories should use commercial Ct testing kits

In this study, four of the in-country laboratories used a GeneXpert (Cepheid) platform for PCR processing of the conjunctival swabs, while one country used a QuantStudio 7 Flex Real-Time PCR machine (Applied Biosystems). Key benefits of using the GeneXpert are that its cartridges contain all the necessary reagents for the detection of the target nucleic acids, while the platform itself has internal quality controls, which help to standardise the performance across labs and monitor the quality of DNA extraction and processing. Conversely, the QuantStudio 7 in this study used a 'homebrew' set of primers and probes, developed by the London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine. Not only is this latter approach difficult to standardise, but the lack of a 'kit' makes it challenging for national programmes to ensure all the supplies are ordered correctly and on time.

Going forward, we recommend the use of commercially available *Ct* testing kits for which there are published data on assay performance. This will help to streamline procurement, standardise data quality and enable the comparison of results between countries.

7. The time-lag between receiving TF and laboratory results should be accounted for in survey planning

While TF results can be quickly analysed in the days and weeks following a survey, the laboratory processing of specimens can add weeks to months to the standard trachoma survey process. Although in this study, it was heartening that for the majority of countries, the serology data took less than a week to process for a given EU.

In this study it was decided that due to cost constraints in the study budget, the testing of swabs would only go ahead in five of the six countries, *if* the TF and serology results were discordant (Figure 1). In one country, *Ct* infection testing was budgeted for from the outset, meaning the infection and serology testing happened concurrently. Going forward, programmes will need to weigh the benefits of having timely results (which

requires an upfront commitment to ordering PCR supplies) versus the potential to avoid unnecessary expense.

Careful planning, to ensure laboratories are ready to process samples in a timely manner and the use of high throughput testing platforms, can help limit delays in accessing results for programmatic decision-making.

Figure 1. Workflow to decision-making for standard trachoma surveys versus 'plus' surveys in the six-country study. The additional time needed for laboratories to process samples collected as part of trachoma 'plus' surveys can delay programmatic decision-making.

8. *The interpretation of results can be challenging in the absence of WHO-approved thresholds*

The study set out to collect data on three indicators:

- i) TF (a clinical sign of active trachoma);
- ii) The seroconversion rate (a measure of cumulative exposure to *Ct* infection derived from antibody testing); and
- iii) *Ct* infection (as measured by PCR).

While WHO has set a threshold for TF prevalence in relation to trachoma elimination,¹ there are currently no formal guidelines for the interpretation of serology and infection

results. This made it challenging for countries to interpret results across the three indicators, especially in instances where data from different indicators were discrepant. Tremendous progress has been made to propose evidence-based thresholds for the serology data,⁷ for which WHO plans to convene a Guideline Development Group. A similar process is now underway to propose thresholds for Ct infection data. In the meantime, countries are encouraged to work with subject matter experts when interpreting results.

Conclusions

This study showed it is possible for countries to both conduct trachoma ‘plus’ surveys and to carry out the associated serology and infection testing using in-country laboratories. ‘Plus’ surveys cost more than standard surveys and require a significant amount of preplanning and coordination during the fieldwork and laboratory stages. Nevertheless, these surveys serve as an important addition to the elimination toolkit and could actually save programmes money in the long run if the results enable them to avoid unnecessary rounds of MDA and additional impact surveys.

Data from the complementary indicators can improve the understanding of trachoma epidemiology, especially in districts with persistent and recrudescing TF, helping countries achieve elimination sooner.

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